

E-Ball Technology

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ABSTRACT

A new concept of pc is coming now that is E-Ball concept pc. The E-Ball concept pc is a sphere shaped computer which is the smallest design among all the laptops and desktops. This computer has all the feature like a traditional computer, elements like keyboard or mouse. dvd,large screen display. E-Ball is designed that pc is be placed on two stands, open by presenting and holding the two buttons located on each side of the E-Ball pc, this pc is the latest concept technology. The E-Ball is a sphere shaped computer concept which is the smallest design among all the laptops and desktops have ever made.

Keywords: sphere shaped, virtual keyboard, Operating System, dual core processor, 250-500 GB HDD

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INTRODUCTION

A computer has progressed tremendously in the field of modern E-ball technology. It has become the basic needs of modern generation. As it many tasks earlier to do, it is used by almost every person who works in the field of technology and in office. A computer is a general purpose device that can be programmed to be carry out a set of arithmetic and logical operations automatically additionally it may be used for many purposes like playing games, watching movies, storing files etc. Now there are many modifications done in the computer, for making it compact and handling like laptops as well we all know, that development and advancement never stops, so still some more modifications are being done. A new concept of PC is coming now that is E-Ball technology

FEATURES OF E-BALL TECHNOLOGY

The E-Ball technology concept PC is a sphere shaped PC which is the smallest design among all the laptops and desktops. This concept PC will measure 160mm in diameter and it was designed for Microsoft Windows Os. The computer has all the features like traditional complete like mouse, DVD, Display, Motherboard, Hard drive, Webcam, modem, LAN and WAN slots. The design of E-Ball is not going to be a PC with all conventional components like mouse, keyboard, normal screen. The concept PC is called E-Ball and

its shaped like a sphere because in Tnokovski's opinion this is the best shape in nature and it draws everybody's attention. E-Ball will feature a dual core processor, 250-500GB HDD, 2GB of RAM, integrated graphic card and sound card, 2 x 50 W speakers, HD-DVD recorder, wireless optical mouse and laser keyboard ,LAN and WLAN card, modem, Web cam and integrated LCD projector. It contains wireless optical mouse and laser keyboard, and LCD projector. It has around 350-600 GB of Hard disk drive. It contains 5 GB RAM. It has two 50W speakers. It has LAN and WLAN card and a Web cam. When you want to carry it around you can easily "pack it" into a ball. This is a futuristic concept, and this, I think, is how the future computers will look like. This device has an optical keyboard and an holographic display. So you dont have a physical but it fits in to the computer when you want to carry it around. The bad thing about using a virtual keyboard is what you need a smooth surface, otherwise I dont know how will you be able to use it. It is strange enough to call this device a computer, because it is so small, but as far as i know it doesnt lack any hardware part and tends to be a future machine found in any house or office. I dont know exactly how this computer will be powered but I think it will have a powerful battery so you will have a great standby time

HISTORY OF E-BALL

Designer Apostol tnikovski has replaced the good old pc for the shackles of the monotonous squares and rectangle shapes with his newly designed wonder in a spherical shape. According to Apostol is the best shape in nature and it draws everybody attention. It is the smallest pc ever made.

SIZE OF E-BALL

- E-Ball is very small, it only has 6 inch diameter sphere
- It has 120mm length and 120mm width motherboard
- Created by Apostopol Tnikovski
- Smallest pc ever made

THE DISPLAY UNIT OF E-BALL

E-Ball concept PC don't have any external display unit, it has a button when you press this a projector will pop-up and it focus the computer screen on the wall which can be adjusted with navigation kehys. If there is no wall then it has a paper sheet holder that divides into three pieces like an umbrella just after popping upland it will show desktop on the paper sheet.

WORKING INTERFACE

WORKING OF E-BALL

E-Ball concept pc has a laser keyboard that is fully a concept keyboard that is visible when the pc is working. The keyboard is not physical- it is interpreted by lasers that appear after you press the respective button. It recognizes your fingers with the help of an IR sensor when you are typing at a particular place, while the mouse is a pop out wonder making this an exciting piece of technology.

The software interface of E-Ball concept pc is highly stylized with icons that can be remembered easily that support all types of windows operating system. E-Ball concept pc work very easy while you are making video presentations, listening music watching large screen movies and chatting on the net.

As years passes, the computer size is becoming smaller. This ball is known as E-Ball and its design is given by Aposotol Tnikovski. He was trying to create smallest pc in the world when he came across this idea. It is shaped like a sphere because in Tnikovski's opinion this is the best shape in nature and it draws everybody's attention. You'll see the pop-out laser mouse, a pico projector inside that illuminates either the wall or a sheet of paper for a screen, and that laser keyboard that would almost certainly be a clumsy input device. Fix that, and find a motherboard that'll fit inside this palm-sized baby, and Apostol might be onto something here. E-Ball will feature a dual core processor, 250-500GB HDD, 2GB of RAM, integrated graphic card and sound card, 2 x 50 W speakers, HD-DVD recorder, wireless optical mouse and laser keyboard, LAN and WLAN card, modem, Web cam and integrated LCD projector

- Press and hold the power button for 5 sec
- Adjusted the LCD projector
- Detach the optical mouse
- Activate the virtual keyboard
- Do whatever you want

VIRTUAL KEYBOARD

A virtual keyboard is a projection keyboard that is projected and touched on any flat surface. A virtual keyboard basically uses the principles of sensor technology and artificial intelligence to let user works in any interface. Whenever we press the keyboard button, it is projected optically on the flat surface and as the user touches the image of the key, the optical device detects the strokes and sends it into computer

ADVANTAGES OF E-BALL

- E-Ball is a portable
- E-Ball has a large memory
- E-Ball is useful for making video presentation

- E-Ball support user defined keyboard layouts
- E-Ball is efficient
- E-Ball is very easy to use
- E-Ball is more secure than other computer

DISADVANTAGES OF E-BALL

- Normal operating system cannot work in the computers
- Cost of E-Ball is very high
- It is difficult to understand if any problems occur in hardware part

CONCLUSION

As the year passes, the computer size becomes smaller. Today's technology is at its peak point beyond what we could ever imagine. New inventions and innovations are emerging on a daily basis.

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